

4Healing and the Social Impact

Research was taken and observed to add to 4Healing by Dr. David Render for a holistic approach to people in the midst of the worst times pandemic COVID-19 and civil unrest and people's hearts failing in America needing healing.

Fred Rogers TV Program Mr. Rogers Neighborhood

Empathy was given in a very different way pioneering of Fred Rogers. A crucially important issue to the very disciplined and poised Mr. Rogers being was a nationally-known figure, Fred Rogers was already a pioneer in public television for children with his neighborly style to the viewers.

In 1969 he appeared before a senate subcommittee to support funding for public broadcasting, which was facing significant budget cuts. Rogers sprung into political action. Although there were many lessons adults had learned and still learning today as well from Rogers. The empathy and passion is amazing to watch much like a doctor of inner needs is amazing on his TV program. Mr. Rogers Neighborhood incorporated many elements and unique soft style include music education, appreciation of art, being accepted on who you are, identity, and a wisdom well of many other important topics, the main thrust of the show was that it allowed viewers to experience the decidedly prosocial behavior of Fred Rogers as he gave freely to promote and instill the values and ethics among his viewership audience. On a day of triumph for a courageous TV Broadcaster, the 1st of May in 1969, Mr. Rogers addressed the Senate to argue that \$20 million in funding for PBS should not be cut. John Pastore, the Senator from Rhode Island who led the hearing, had never seen nor hear of Mr. Rogers' television show. Rogers shared empathy and social and emotional Intelligence as he shared what was important to millions of people and children for enriching public television. Mr. Rogers single -handedly made his plea in just six minutes to convince the Grinch of an attitude and impatient Senator from Rhode Island that the \$20 million was well worth it (Bradberry 2014). Mr. Rogers taken on racial lines with Mr. Clemons, Mr. Rogers shared about the children need helpers. Mr. Rogers to make things special, by you being you. With all the empathy and emotional Intelligence contributed nearly 10 Million dollars' net worth est.

Mr. Fred Rogers Scores 20 Million Dollars- Entertainment and Media Transcript Commentary Review Involving Empathy and Emotional Intelligence

Senate Commerce Committee Speech Statement on PBS Funding 1 May 1969

Senator Pastore: Alright Rogers, you've got the floor.

Mr. Rogers: Senator Pastore, this is a philosophical statement and would take about ten minutes to read, so I'll not do that. One of the first things that a child learns in a healthy family is trust, and I trust what you have said that you will read this. It's very important to me. I care deeply about children.

Senator Pastore: Will it make you happy if you read it?

Mr. Rogers: I'd just like to talk about it, if it's alright. My first children's program was on WQED fifteen years ago, and its budget was \$30. Now, with the help of the Sears-Roebuck Foundation and National Educational Television, as well as all of the affiliated stations -- each station pays to show our program. It's a unique kind of funding in educational television. With this help, now our program has a budget of \$6000. It may sound like quite a difference, but \$6000 pays for less than two minutes of cartoons. Two minutes of animated, what I sometimes say, bombardment. I'm very much concerned, as I know you are, about what's being delivered to our children in this country. And I've worked in the field of child development for six years now, trying to understand the inner needs of children. We deal with such things as -- as the inner drama of childhood. We don't have to bop somebody over the head to...make drama on the screen. We deal with such things as getting a haircut, or the feelings about brothers and sisters, and the kind of anger that arises in simple family situations. And we speak to it constructively.

Senator Pastore: How long of a program is it?

Mr. Rogers: It's a half hour every day. Most channels schedule it in the noontime as well as in the evening. WETA here has scheduled it in the late afternoon.

Senator Pastore: Could we get a copy of this so that we can see it? Maybe not today, but I'd like to see the program.

Mr. Rogers: I'd like very much for you to see it.

Senator Pastore: I'd like to see the program itself, or any one of them.

Mr. Rogers: We made a hundred programs for EEN, the Eastern Educational Network, and then when the money ran out, people in Boston and Pittsburgh and Chicago all came to the fore and said we've got to have more of this neighborhood expression of care. And this is what -- This is what I give. I give an expression of care every day to each child, to help him realize that he is unique. I end the program by saying, "You've made this day a special day, by just your being you. There's no

person in the whole world like you, and I like you, just the way you are." And I feel that if we in public television can only make it clear that feelings are mentionable and manageable, we will have done a great service for mental health. I think that it's much more dramatic that two men could be working out their feelings of anger -- much more dramatic than showing something of gunfire. I'm constantly concerned about what our children are seeing, and for 15 years I have tried in this country and Canada, to present what I feel is a meaningful expression of care.

Senator Pastore: Do you narrate it?

Mr. Rogers: I'm the host, yes. And I do all the puppets and I write all the music, and I write all the scripts

-- Senator Pastore: Well, I'm supposed to be a pretty tough guy, and this is the first time I've had goose bumps for the last two days.

Mr. Rogers: Well, I'm grateful, not only for your goose bumps, but for your interest in -- in our kind of communication. Could I tell you the words of one of the songs, which I feel is very important?

Senator Pastore: Yes.

Mr. Rogers: This has to do with that good feeling of control, which I feel that children need to know is there. And it starts out, "What do you do with the mad that you feel?" And that first line came straight from a child. I work with children doing puppets in -- in very personal communication with small groups: What do you do with the mad that you feel? When you feel so mad you could bite. When the whole wide world seems oh so wrong, and nothing you do seems very right. What do you do? Do you punch a bag? Do you pound some clay or some dough? Do you round up friends for a game of tag or see how fast you go? It's great to be able to stop when you've planned a thing that's wrong. And be able to do something else instead, and think this song -- 'I can stop when I want to. Can stop when I wish. Can stop, stop, stop anytime....And what a good feeling to feel like this! And know that the feeling is really mine. Know that there's something deep inside that helps us become what we can. For a girl can be someday a lady, and a boy can be someday a man.'

Senator Pastore: I think it's wonderful. I think it's wonderful. Looks like you just earned the 20 million dollars.

Transcript Commentary Review

Mr. Rogers starts off slow and winding about a child and the family impact. Starting from \$30.00 budget in educational television. Mr. Rogers not only shares an empathetic tone and discipline in his presentation on his show. He does an amazing job of speaking about his 30-minute show. Mr. Roger then speaks on what happened when the money ran out of this 'Neighborhood Expression of Care' and sharing about special and uniqueness. He opened a door of great social contribution in Public Television about violence or anger. 15 years he presented in US and Canada. Mr. Rogers is "Grateful in the kind of communication" Roger states. Rogers deals with personal Communication of children. The wealth that was rewarded after sharing Empathy and emotional Intelligence all because he cared enough to dedicate his life toward this caused millions of people now benefit to this day.

Oprah Winfrey Case Studies

Case uses interviews with Oprah Winfrey Business case scholarly articles and media videos on the independent research of the daytime icon of her major media empire. Success shares the footprints on how it was obtained for those that dare to take the journey. It is evident that Oprah life was not just given success but forged path pre- Harpo Productions. (Lagace 2006) Oprah's story is one that says that you can start from scratch and become a multi-billionaire mogul. Winfrey's humble beginnings was in Kosciusko Mississippi humble beginnings. Oprah lived with her grandmother after her parents split. Hattie Mae Lee taught her the Bible and all the stories about righteousness. Oprah was inspired helping those in need. What you see today things were of a different place and space beck in the 50's and 60's for Winfrey. When it came to corporate models Oprah did not follow any corporate models yet her gut feeling about things. She had declined offers from many companies such as AT&T, Intel and Ralph Lauren to be on their boards, stating that 'she did not understand what she would do on their boards.' She knew she was in the business of soothing souls. Whether it was from magazines, book clubs, viewers or consumers. Millions of people found healing through her television show. The level of empathy in the mind of Oprah goes back through the path of her young childhood and launching to her entertainment career in television, the processing of staggering success goes years back in Winfrey's own reflection personal account between passages in

her turbulent childhood, both beneficial and traumatic, that became milestone lessons for her viewers audience and later guided her business and philanthropic activities.

Millions all over the world have been curious and follow about the motivations behind a business career, the value of authenticity in leadership, and the origins of unique abilities. We have seen such generosity and social empathy to share stories from people's lives from so many different walks of life. (George and Mclean 2005.)

Oprah had a God-given gift to get all kinds of people in the room on her TV program and viewer that also African American and white viewers. It's no accident that Oprah's success has spread all over the world where writers glean from her ability to craft masterfully the masses in deep dramatic stories of people. Davis writes in research article journal of Cultural Studies involving a study of Oprah's Book Program, "Although cross-racial sympathy can often devolve into a colonizing appropriation, my reception analysis underscores the important role that empathetic crossings within cultural space can play in the development of anti-racist coalitions." (Davis 2004). It is argued in a unique point of view in *The Secret of Her Success: Oprah Winfrey and the Seductions of Self-Transformation*, journal article that Oprah Winfrey's professed mission to "empower" her followers — in which she routinely favors private initiatives and individual self-improvement over public funding and collective responsibility for societal needs, and thereby a deflection technique attention from the more larger stemmed issues of social inequality and distributional politics in America — and considers the class and gender basis of the appeal of this project for her predominantly white, middle- and upper middle class female following (Peck 2009). Which Oprah has made it work very well across many people around the globe.

Media Interviews with Oprah closer look

Oprah speaks about Life Advice, problems and issues in listed problems about not being able to fix everything. Decision to use your life, service, speak up, show up, volunteer, help and offer talent. Bigger moments happen through small moments. Oprah speaks that she wants to be a service to the viewer since 1989 and onward. People watched and raised up on the show. Radical love and gratitude. She said its 10 x better than what people think. She had an appreciation of her life and was speaking to her to a path made clear.

Clayton Moss

Shares visual closet and cage how the boy was tightly bound as affect to the audience. His family would rub fecal matter and be urinated on. Oprah shares empathy and passion about Clayton Moss Story.

Jessica Coleman

Oprah masterfully shares the depth and intimacy of people's lives. And tells the play by play of the media segments with intensity and also curiosity to here more, leaving viewers on the edge of their seats. Her poise and emotions under control in the most dramatic of situations on screen speaking to Jessica via satellite from Lorain County Jail.

Whitney Houston

Oprah connects with Oprah Winfrey asking the hard questions about rehab Bobby Brown and drug addiction. There is such a cohesive that shows on screen with Whitney. Connecting with speaking about God and the Gift that was given to Whitney and how it faded from her life and she wanted the moments back with the trauma. She spoke about getting the peace and joy in life. Oprah shared about the Treasure that was given how it got squandered away. Oprah does a great job of showing Houston's humanity.

Woman Terrified of People

Oprah speaks with a woman who is in a real social prison by being terrified on such a scale by being in public. She is not able to function with daily things due to being trapped and confined.

Michael Jackson and Elizabeth Taylor

Oprah shares about the days way back in time of the former time on who he was. Michael recollects James Brown was such a motivation of talent singing and dancing for Michael growing up. Oprah shares the tough questions on happiness how Michael Jackson was happy on stage but off stage and was sad and lonely. He did not want to deal with fame. He shares about the other side giving of himself. The price of fame weighed heavy and how his childhood was lost. She probed was it really lost. Michael was very comfortable to talk about his childhood.

“Oprah Winfrey arguably has more influence on the culture than any university president, politician, political or religious leader, except perhaps the pope.”

- Vanity Fair Magazine, in 1994.

"She (Oprah) may be uncomfortable talking about it (money), but when it comes to making it, she sure knows what she's doing."

- Fortune Magazine, in March 2002

Case Study Oprah & Benedictine Monk Interview Analysis

Oprah shares this amazing opportunity to speak with this man almost 100 years old sharing a lot of wisdom. Brother David shares the simplicity of life. He shares the many opportunities to grow. Oprah speaks about you should not have to break a limb or get a disease to see grateful living. The dissension and brokenness has to be stretched on such a level us take on empathy. Hope is different from our Hopes. Being open to surprise to open the heart. To unlock the path, you have to trust life. Ultimately what faith is. How can people develop faith when life has been not very fair? The only thing you can do is trust life. David shares people can look back on life there has been a turn around. When things have been utterly terrible. Knowing this is encouraging. Developing a trust in life knowing that you can get through it. Even though we don't see it life will gives us good things. Oprah and David shares about a fast life and not see the amazing opportunities. You have to stop and look and be present and go and grab it. Enjoy the moment. 1.Stop 2. Look and 3. Go. Aliveness when it comes you are willing to share, inspiration to a revolution can happen. We want to stay impressed that have to be repeated. Gratitude can inspire a revolution you're not violent, or operating under scarcity. The Power Pyramid is dangerous if we are fearful. Fearfulness is violence. Fearful in another sense or oppression happens that the other will get ahead rivalry, competition and Greed. Peace and cooperation and needed in our world. Both share this is an opportunity to love our opportunities. Working definition of LOVE, the common denomination is yes we belong together. "Love is a lived yes to belonging." An aspect of listening to your enemy lets together to look at the issues not their position and common ground. Oprah opens the door about the great calling. The great mystery being GOD and life. Life offers you things that nobody else has. Fingerprint and hairs on your head and the soul personality. People want to come alive in their uniqueness. David shares about being in the German Army is in such a peaceful manner. Even in the next hour we do not even know what will happen. This is true. He did not expect to last past 20 years old. Living in the present moment gives joy. Even with all the hardship he would not trade it for the world. Thus Brother David became a Benedictine Monk.

“Finding unique diamonds in the rough is a reality, you just have to have the right sight in your heart to see what is not there and should be there”.

